

ORGANIZATIONAL MIGRATION IN SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. In the context of the development of the economy of Uzbekistan, the migration movement of labor resources, reasons, migration problems, population employment problems, food and other issues were considered in this article.

Key words. Migration, internal migration, external migration, permanent migration, seasonal migration, fluctuating migration, migration intensity, national composition, "brain drain", migration flow.

The demographic situation in each country has a direct impact on economic, political, and social processes. An increase in the birth rate after a certain period of time will have an effect on the corresponding changes in employment in the labor market and on the level of spending of the state budget on social needs, as well as on the functioning of the education and health systems.

The world population includes two types of people depending on their age: working-age 15-60-year-olds, working-age children, and the elderly. About 70 percent of the total population belongs to the first type, but this share varies in different regions. In turn, the working population is divided into two: economically active and inactive. Economically inactive include housewives, students (on vacation), dependents, and stateless persons. We are interested in the economically active population, that is, people who are able to work and who want to work. This category of citizens actively participates in the process of job search within the country and abroad. Although international labor migration has a long history, it became one of the leading manifestations of the movement of factors of production only in the 20th century.

Most of us live with our own family in the community, and if that family has more than 1 worker, the impact of migration on income can be different. Cohabiting

workers often make joint decisions: therefore, in such cases, the family may agree to move only if the migration leads to an increase in the incomes of all family members. Of course, if the salary of one of the family members decreases, but the salary of the other one increases by more than this, the total income of the family may increase. Analyzing family migration, a new concept emerges - forced migrants: such migrants move to other countries for family reasons and not for increased income.

Migration can be attributed to the following reasons:

- internationalization of economic life;
- socio-demographic changes;
- revolution in the field of science, technology and information;
- development of integration processes;
- activities of transnational corporations.

The export of labor resources has both positive and negative consequences for the national economy. First of all, this is related to the so-called "departure of smart people" leaving abroad of highly qualified specialists. The essence of this process is that specialists leave countries with a low standard of living for countries that can provide high wages, good working conditions, sufficient conditions for the realization of creative opportunities, and finally social guarantees.

In order to understand the composition of the international migration circulation, it is necessary to define the manifestations of labor migration, which can be classified according to various criteria. The main manifestations of migration are as follows:

- according to duration - temporary, seasonal and permanent;
- according to social structure - unskilled workers, middle technical and service workers, students (during vacation), experts, science, culture and sports figures, entrepreneurs;
- according to its nature - directly and indirectly (within the TMC within the company);
- according to the labor contract - individual and collective;

- according to the legal status in the receiving country - assimilation (subsequent citizenship) and non-assimilation.

According to international statistics, the majority of migrants are low-skilled workers employed in production and agriculture. Nevertheless, the migration flow of specialists, i.e., highly qualified labor force occupying important and highly paid positions in the structure of TNCs, is growing (we are talking about the "departure of the smart").

In addition, the mobilization of women and youth in integrated associations such as the European Union is increasing year by year.

Regarding labor migration caused by socio-economic goals and its impact on demography, among the factors that force citizens to look for work outside their homeland, the main one is their desire to improve their standard of living and use their skills effectively. At the same time, negative socio-economic phenomena such as unemployment, population increase in agriculture cause a temporary or permanent change of place of residence.

The process of population aging is typical for Uzbekistan. The analysis of the modern trends of demographic processes in the republic shows that the proportion of children in the age structure of the population is decreasing, and the proportion of working-age and elderly people is increasing. This, in turn, requires the implementation of specific changes in the direction of the socio-economic development of the country in the future, the development of projects and programs for the social protection of the elderly, taking into account the territorial and gender aspects of the aging population. The implementation of these measures depends on defining the perspective of demographic development. Taking this into account, the long-term demographic forecast of Uzbekistan until 2025 was implemented using the "age shift" method.

Demographic policy involves measures aimed at regulating the reproduction of the population, achieving its optimal quantity and quality characteristics. In practice, this means repeating a healthy generation. Demographic development programs should be comprehensive, cover a wide range of factors of social life, and

take into account the consequences of demographic processes. Therefore, the problems of the world's population are a constant focus of the United Nations. The UN conducts research in the field of population studies, including problems of the interaction of demographic, economic and social processes, assists countries in developing and implementing demographic programs, holds world conferences on various issues of population studies.

Labor migration is a process characteristic of almost all national economies. However, its intensity varies significantly in one or another region of the world. The most intensive flow of labor migrants is observed when there is a significant difference in the level of socio-economic development and the rate of natural demographic growth of the labor force exporting/importing countries. Among the four main directions of migration, the migration of labor forces from developing countries to developed countries takes the first place in terms of the total migration flow.

In conclusion, migration has both positive and negative consequences. The positive consequences are that the population is provided with work, the lifestyle of the population improves, foreign currency flows into the country, and the population achieves economic stability. As for the negative consequences, the impact of work on health, the loneliness of the family, problems with raising children may arise. Therefore, it is necessary to perfect the migration issues.

List of used literature

1. Ш.М.Мирзиёевнинг “2019-2021 йилларда Ўзбекистон Республикасини инновацион ривожлантириш стратегиясини тасдиқлаш тўғрисида”ги фармони
2. Ш.М.Мирзиёев «Ташқи меҳнат миграциясини тартибга солиш» ҳақидаги қарори Тошкент 2018 йил 5 июль.
3. Абдурахмонов Қ.Х “Меҳнат иқтисодиёти” дарслик Тошкент 2012 й.
4. Макконел К.Р., Брю С.Л. Экономикс: принципы, проблемы и политика. - Т.2. - М: Республика, 1992. - 400 с.

5. “Янги Меҳнат иқтисодиёти: назария ва амалиёт” / Роналд
Г.Эхренберг 2012 йил, 278 б.

Websites:

1. www.kun.uz
2. www.worldbank.com
3. www.lex.uz
4. www.ziyonet.uz
5. www.Uzbekistan24.uz
6. www.uza.uz
7. www.norma.uz
8. www.migration.uz
9. www.mehnat.uz